

Twelve Month Report 2021

JRP13-AMRSH5- WORLD COM

Responsible Partner: NUI Galway

Contributing partners:

NUI Galway

University of Surrey

University of Tartu

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VISAVET Complutense Univ. of
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GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM

1. Summary of the work carried out

500 words, 1 page. Please emphasize the main scientific results and outcomes. This part will be used and published in other public deliverables, for instance the annual report. It should therefore be a standalone and clear as a separate document.

One Health EJP WORLDCOM aims to develop diagnostic tools linked with mobile referencing technology for detection of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in zoonotic pathogens. Resulting technologies will enable rapid on-site detection of AMR in pathogens from animal and human populations, facilitating early investigation of emerging resistances and development of machine-learning algorithms for AMR prediction.

Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) enzymes produced by *Enterobacteriaceae* organisms confer resistance to beta-lactam antimicrobials presenting a major public health concern. Biomarker genes for highly prevalent ESBLs, cefotaximase (CTX-M), oxacillinase (OXA), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* carbapenemase (KPC) and New Delhi metallo-beta-lactamase (NDM), were selected as assay development targets for AMR identification. An internally controlled multiplex Loop-primer endonuclease cleavage - loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay was developed for differential detection of closely related CTX-M variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, associated with animal and human infection, respectively. A singleplex LEC-LAMP assay was also developed for differential detection of closely related OXA variants, *bla*_{OXA-48} and *bla*_{OXA-181/232}, as a precursor to multiplex assay development. AMR LAMP assays have been developed and validated targeting important AMR r genes (MCR-1, KPC, OXA-48, OXA-23 and VIM) that are associated with zoonotic bacterial infections. The assays are able to detect target genes within 10 min, with 100% sensitivity and specificity.

In relation to sample preparation, a rapid protocol for on-site DNA isolation was successfully developed and validated using confirmed CTX-M-1 positive porcine faecal samples. There has also been significant progress with water sample preparation for LAMP detection of pathogens and AMR genes. The method is rapid (30 min), and sensitive with a detection limit of 10 cfu/mL. The method allowed consistent LAMP detection of all the target AMR genes from tap and pond water spiked with different Gram-negative bacterial cultures within 35 min of the sample preparation.

Targeted and whole-genome sequencing of AMR strains has progressed. Progress includes NGS data generated from: 24 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from alpacas or llamas, and 138 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from pigs reared in Germany, containing a range of *bla* AMR genotypes; 390 *E. coli* isolates from diverse sources (110 from human, 144 from swine and 136 from broilers) and 43 *E. coli* isolates from river and wastewater confirming the presence of CTX-M genes and the colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* among the these *E. coli* isolates, including isolates co-producing colistin resistance and CTX-M genes.

Significant progress has been made concerning the automated assessment of colorimetric LAMP assays for AMR genes, employing an image processing pipeline combined with a machine learning method. This procedure remains robust against background noise, making it suitable for on-site use as part of a mobile detection kit, and has been implemented as an Android smart phone app for portability. This includes automatically annotating these data and communicating the results with a cloud storage service.

456 words

2. Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

5000 words, 10 pages. Please provide enough detail to understand the work done per task. All aspects should be discussed, scientific and others (integrative activities, etc.). Please indicate if the task is ongoing or completed and if any delay can be expected. Please note that all the WP and tasks due in the period M37 to M49 should figure below.

WP: 1 Generation of up to date sequence information for selected pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes

JRP13-WP1-T1- Analysis of publically available sequences for antimicrobial resistance genes associated with Salmonella, Campylobacter and E. coli

This task was completed in Year 3.

JRP13-WP1-T2- Targeted and whole genome de novo sequencing of phenotypically characterised isolates from various settings

NUIG generated genomic nucleotide sequence data from sequencing locally isolated *E. coli* CTX-M environmental samples and provided this sequence data to a WORLDCOM AMR gene database for use in assay development. This nucleotide sequence information included CTX-M-1 (n=2), CTX-M-4 (n=4), CTX-M-9 (n=1), CTX-M-15 (n=24), CTX-M-27 (n=5) and CTX-M-65 (n=1) *E. coli* isolates.

At the UoS, no whole genome sequencing (WGS) has been performed due to the COVID-19 lock down and difficulty in obtaining samples and publicly available genome databases have been utilised. However, a collaboration with a clinician has been established and the samples collection has been started. The task is still ongoing.

At FLI, 24 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from alpacas or llamas in Central Germany were short-read whole genome sequenced. Eighteen isolates contained the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} allele, three the *bla*_{CTX-M-27} allele, two the *bla*_{CMY-2} allele and one each a *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, a *bla*_{CTX-M-65} or a *bla*_{SHV-12} allele. Additionally, 138 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from pigs raised in Central Germany were short-read whole genome sequenced. Sequence analysis and gene quantification is still ongoing, but we have identified several isolates with the *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CTX-M-55} and *bla*_{CTX-M-27} alleles, each. FLI has a manuscript under revision describing the isolation and phenotypic characterisation of the *E. coli* isolates from alpacas and llamas and is currently preparing a manuscript for publication describing their WGS characterization in more detail.

At the UT, *de novo* WGS continued, 96 *E. coli* genomes were *de novo* assembled and AMR genes annotated in December 2021, and additional 106 *E. coli* genomes were sequenced at local sequencing core facility and are currently under processing in bioinformatic pipeline. Long read sequencing protocol using Oxford Nanopore technology is under the development and tested for closing draft genomes successfully. Manuscript about *de novo* WGS of *Campylobacter* spp. has been accepted by Poultry Science (Elsevier).

At UCM, a total of 390 *E. coli* isolates from diverse sources (110 from human, 144 from swine and 136 from broilers) were sequencing using a MiSeq Illumina platform. An *in silico* analysis of acquired

antimicrobial resistance was performed, showing the presence of CTX-M genes among the 390 *E. coli* isolates, specifically four isolates contained the *bla*_{CTX-M-15} allele, two the *bla*_{CTX-M-14} allele and one the *bla*_{CTX-M-27} allele. In addition, 10 isolates showed the presence of the colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* (9 from swine and 1 from broiler). Of these 10 isolates, 5 of them co-produced colistin resistance and CTX-M genes. Additionally, 43 *E. coli* isolates from environmental water (river and wastewater) bearing 16S rRNA 16S methyltransferases were sequenced using Illumina and Nanopore technology. The presence of CTX-M genes was observed in the wastewater samples, with 72% (n = 18) were CTX-M-55 producing, while the presence of CTX-M genes was not observed in the river samples. Of the 18 CTX-M-55 positive samples from wastewater, 16 also showed *mcr-1* gene. The results were published in Communications Biology and uploaded to Zenodo repository (DOI: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x and <https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR>).

During July 2021 a OHEJP Short Term Mission was undertaken by Liam Burke (NUIG) who travelled to Worldcom partner UCM to train in Nanopore sequencing and hybrid sequence analysis for plasmid characterization. The STM resulted in the generation of Nanopore sequence data for a collection of 41 carbapenemase producing (*bla*_{KPC-2}, *bla*_{NDM-5} and *bla*_{OXA-48}) Enterobacterales isolates. All strains were first isolated during 2018-2020 in Galway from natural water environments (rivers, estuaries, sea), hospital and municipal wastewaters, the hospital environment and hospital patients. A cyberattack at NUI Galway greatly impacted project progress between October and December, hampering completion of sequencing. However complete Nanopore data and hybrid assemblies are now available for all strains and annotation and analysis of carbapenemase plasmids and CPE genomes is ongoing. A manuscript will be prepared by the collaborating partners in early 2022.

At INSA a total of 231 *de novo* WGS runs were performed using a MiSeq Illumina platform, namely on 11 *Acinetobacter* genomes from human origin, as well as on other bacteria from different reservoirs such as: 38 *E. coli* from human, 8 from bivalves, 3 from gilthead, 12 from water; 139 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from human, 2 from gilthead, 10 from hospital environment, 10 from water. Overall, these bacteria have *bla*_{OXA-23}, *bla*_{OXA-48}, *bla*_{NDM}, *bla*_{CTX}, *bla*_{SHV}, *bla*_{TEM}, and/or *mcr*-type genes. Aquaculture bacteria (from bivalves and gilthead) are being included in a PhD thesis with respective manuscript that is in preparation.

Meanwhile, UCM and UT are leading creating and sharing a database draft, with the support of UoS, among the WorldCOM partners to develop a resource of all isolates, their resistance profile and sequences to facilitate sharing of all relevant information. The database draft is currently being further developed and all important and frequently reported ESBL, carbapenem and mobile colistin-mediated resistance genes are included.

This task is ongoing.

JRP13-WP1-T3- Development of machine learning algorithms for the prediction of anti-microbial resistance. (University of Surrey, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM)

At the UoS, the machine learning algorithm studies have two aims: 1) developing algorithms for automating LAMP detection, reducing personnel biases and the need for expertise to analyse the results, and 2) development of algorithms for the prediction of AMR from WGS.

For the first aim, algorithms have been developed in collaboration with WP2-T1, specifically for the automated detection of AMR genes based on fluorescence and colorimetric LAMP assays image data. For the fluorescence-based detection, amplification and annealing data series were used as the input for a multi-modal neural network model trained using logistic regression. This model was trained and tested using a total of 56 samples, and leave-one-out cross validation estimated a test accuracy of ~ 98 %. With respect to colorimetric-based detection, images of tested samples (e.g. targeting *mcr-1* and *KPC* genes) were used to train a nearest centroid classifier algorithm to automatically identify colour changes. The images for the samples were pre-processed using colour-based

thresholding and contour edge detection to extract representative features for the algorithm. Moreover, a hierarchical clustering technique, agglomerative clustering, has been introduced to provide robustness against background noise. This algorithm has been successfully validated using noisy image data and has since been ported into an Android smartapp for on-site applications.

Concerning the second aim commitment of this work package task, predicting antimicrobial resistance using WGS, progress has been delayed due to the other commitments for this work package, the delayed employment date alongside COVID-19 related restrictions. To date, a data preparation technique for performing dimensionality reduction on WGS data has been identified from the recent literature, based on forming 'k-mer-based representations' and 'compacted de Bruijn graphs', to reduce the number of input features from ~85 million to ~1 million per sample, in some cases. We plan to pursue this strategy further and identify a suitable supervised learning method for predicting AMR and especially EBSL in zoonotic pathogens. Also, no WGS has been performed, but this task is going to be developed first using publicly available sequences and those from our developed database from WP1-T2 as training for the algorithm. Suitable isolates for WGS have now been identified and will be transferred to the UoS in early 2022. This task is still ongoing.

WP2: Assay Development

JRP13-WP2-T1- Development and performance evaluation of singleplex isothermal amplification assays for selected AMR gene targets

NUIG completed the design and development of singleplex Loop-primer endonuclease cleavage - Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assays for the detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, using existing genomic sequence data from *E. coli* isolates collected and processed by NUIG. Sequence alignment analysis was used to identify single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) differences between both variants, which were then used to develop variant specific LEC-LAMP assays for differential target detection. A separate LEC-LAMP assay for the detection of an internal amplification control (IAC) was also developed. Complete analytical specificity for each assay was established. Analytical sensitivity testing for each assay demonstrated rapid low limits-of-detection with 10 genome copies detected in under 20 min. These assays were used in WP2 Task 3 to develop an internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay. NUIG have completed the design and development of a singleplex LEC-LAMP assay for detection of the OXA variant, *bla*_{OXA-48}. Initial assay evaluation has demonstrated fast low-level detection of 10 genome copies in under 20 min, with specific differential detection from closely related variants *bla*_{OXA-181} and *bla*_{OXA-232}.

At the UoS, five loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) assays had been developed targeting 1) *mcr-1*, 2) *bla*_{OXA-48} and *bla*_{OXA-48-like} genes (OXA-48-, OXA-232-, OXA-181- and OXA-54-encoding genes), 3) *bla*_{OXA-23}, 4) *bla*_{KPC} and 5) *bla*_{VIM}. All five assays had been optimised and validated against a wide range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains to confirm sensitivity and specificity. All five assays showed 100% sensitivity and specificity, and were detected in less than 10 min. The assays were developed and detected both fluorescently and colorimetric. The LAMP detection limit had also been assessed using *mcr-1* LAMP. The detection limit of *mcr-1* LAMP was assessed using a 10-fold and 2-fold serial dilutions of genomic DNA of *E. coli* NCTC 13846 and shown to be 0.0625 pg of DNA, which was successfully amplified in duplicates in less than 8 min. LAMP primers were also designed targeting *mcr-8*, *mcr-9* and the most frequent alleles of *bla*_{IMP} (imipenem metallo-β-lactamase), and will be validated for *mcr-8*, *mcr-9* and *bla*_{IMP}-encoding resistant strains.

JRP13-WP2-T2- Evaluation and selection of sample preparation methods for use with laboratory on-site tests

NUIG completed the development and evaluation of a rapid sample preparation protocol, a 15 min Chelex/heat lysis DNA extraction method, for on-site DNA extraction from animal faecal samples.

Validation of this method was carried out using porcine faecal samples supplied by FLI. These samples were previously collected and confirmed positive for CTX-M-1 by selecting cultures from Gassner agar plates containing 4 µg/ml Ceftiofur, followed by bacterial DNA extraction and PCR using *bla*_{CTX-M-1} family-specific primers with Sanger-sequencing. Samples contained varying amounts of coliform strains resistant to Ceftiofur, ranging from 25-100%. 200 mg of each sample was processed using the rapid sample preparation protocol, followed by LEC-LAMP testing. All samples successfully tested positive for CTX-M-1 in under 20 min.

At the UoS, the water sample preparation method has been further developed and validated. The method is advantageous in being rapid (30 min). The detection limit of the method was further assessed using tap water spiked with the *mcr-1* positive *E. coli* NCTC 13846 bacterial culture at different concentrations (10^7 – 10 cfu/mL). The assay detected up to 10 cfu/mL, as confirmed by culture, of spiked bacterial cells in less than 6 min of the LAMP assay. The water sample preparation method was also validated using tap water spiked with different bacterial cultures of MCR-1 (*E. coli* NCTC 13846), OXA-48 (*E. coli* NCTC 14321), OXA-23 (*A. baumannii* NCTC 13301), KPC (*K. pneumoniae* NCTC 13809 and *E. coli* NCTC 14321) and VIM (*E. cloacae* NCTC 14326) positive strains separately before detection with the AMR LAMP assays. All AMR targets were detected in less than 4 min of the AMR LAMP assays and within 35 min of sample preparation. The method was further validated using pond water samples and we demonstrated successful amplification of bacterial strains used to spike the samples (none of the tested AMR markers were present in the unspiked pond water). All assays were also confirmed using a validated real-time PCR detection assay for the target AMR genes. This task along with WP2-T1 is currently being written as a manuscript for submission in early 2022.

We also implemented the faecal sample preparation method, developed by NUIG, for the direct colorimetric detection of AMR genes from pig faeces. The preliminary results showed successful color change (amplification) with pig faecal samples that were spiked with target bacterial isolates, while un-spiked faecal samples were negative. This method will be further validated using real-time PCR detection and expanded using an extended sample size.

The UoS is currently preparing a manuscript for publication detailing the assay development and evaluations of the five AMR LAMP targets (MCR-1, KPC, OXA-48, OXA-23 and VIM) for the detection of AMR from pathogens and water samples for One Health diagnostic applications.

JRP13-WP2-T3- Development and performance evaluation of multiplex assays for pathogens and resistance genes

NUIG completed the development and evaluation of an internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}. The internally controlled LEC-LAMP assay contains fluorescently labelled primer/probes specific to each target: FAM for *bla*_{CTX-M-1}; HEX for *bla*_{CTX-M-15}; and Cy5 for the IAC. The LEC-LAMP assay demonstrated complete analytical specificity and differential detection of both variants when tested with environmental *E. coli* isolates collected from Ireland and animal *E. coli* isolates from Central Germany: CTX-M-1 (n=15); CTX-M-15 (n=37); and other CTX-Ms (n=12). The LEC-LAMP assay also demonstrated low-level detection for each variant at 10 genome copies per reaction in approximately 20 min. Initial evaluation work to combine the singleplex *bla*_{OXA-48} LEC-LAMP assay with the IAC LEC-LAMP, developing an internally controlled multiplex assay, has been carried out and this work is still on-going. Following this step, simplex and multiplex assays will be evaluated by the remaining partners of this WP (UoS, UT, FLI, INSA) using various sample types, including human, animal and water sources.

To date, FLI has tested the multiplex LEC-LAMP assay on 248 *E. coli* strains isolated from porcine faecal samples and resistant to Ceftiofur. Of these, 157 were positive for *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and 89 for *bla*_{CTX-M-15}. Two negative strains contain a sequence-verified *bla*_{CTX-M-27} allele. WGS analysis shows that *bla*_{CTX-M-55} positive strains score as *bla*_{CTX-M-15} positive, due to the fact that the SNPs differentiating between *bla*_{CTX-M-55} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} are located at the 3' end of the gene and, thus, not subject to discrimination by the primers used in the assay. FLI is currently testing faecal samples from pigs and alpacas for resistance

to carbapenems or colistin to identify strains for validation of the assays developed by UoS and NUIG. NUIG is currently preparing a manuscript for publication detailing the development and evaluation of the internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, from porcine faecal samples.

WP3: Development of Lateral Flow Diagnostics Detection and Mobile Communication system

JRP13-WP3-T1- Development of lateral flow diagnostics for AMR detection

At the UoS, AMR LAMP assays have been developed using both fluorescence and colorimetric signals to allow for the immediate detection of the results. With the current developments and the excellent assays performance we are postponing the decision to develop lateral flow detection as it may be redundant and not necessary. However, we plan to expand the current pathogen and AMR LAMP assay targets to further develop a platform that can detect up to ten AMR genes and identify new pathogens of important zoonotic significance. This will significantly improve our developed LAMP platform and enhance its application for the detection of zoonotic pathogens and associated AMR.

JRP13-WP3-T2- Development of mobile technology for communication of on-site results

At the UoS, a mobile smart app targeting Android phones has been developed which can automatically process and categorise captured images of colorimetric LAMP assays targeting AMR genes. This work package task is closely related to JRP13-WP1-T3 for which image processing and machine learning algorithms have been designed for the purposes of automated on-site detection of AMR. The mobile smart app developed for this task will be able to communicate results to an online cloud storage service: including captured images and associated metadata. This task is close to completion.

WP4: Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed

JRP13-WP4-T1- Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests for detection of pathogens and resistance genes

NUIG is currently developing a mobile diagnostics workstation for the on-site demonstration and application of the developed rapid sample preparation protocol and internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay. Portable instrumentation has recently been procured for the development of this unit. Evaluation of the mobile diagnostics workstation will be carried out on-site using previously confirmed CTX-M-1 positive porcine faecal samples provide by FLI, and bovine faecal sample provided by UT.

FLI has so far acquired 34 composite faecal samples from eight different pig farms representing all stages of a pig fattening cycle and characterized them for cephalosporin (*bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}) and colistin resistance. To validate the sample preparation methods with respect to sensitivity and detection limit, the samples were quantified for total numbers of coliforms and cephalosporin-resistant coliforms. The LEC-LAMP multiplex assay will be used to test both DNA directly isolated from the faecal samples and DNA isolated from enriched cultures. This will allow to estimate the sensitivity and detection limits from field samples with a wide range of coliform counts and percentages of resistant isolates.

JRP13-WP4-T2- Generation of information for dissemination

Depending on the results of isolation protocol and assay validation and testing, SOPs will be drafted and disseminated among the WorldCOM partners for further validation and optimization.

WP5: Project Management

JRP13-WP5-T1-Project Management

Regular virtual (ZOOM) consortium meetings were held over the year and a WorldCOM consortium annual review meeting was held on September 20th 2021.

The WorldCOM DMP received positive feedback from the DMP Committee team during July 2021. It was noted that the Worldcom DMP was well developed, with a good understanding about how to use the template. Reviewer's individual comments for improvement were implemented in the online tool. The online tool is now being updated again ahead of the next review on the 24th January. Comments will be answered and DMP finalised by the 21st of February 2022.

3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

The following list refers to the deliverables and milestones as mentioned in the successive project Annual Work Plans. This part of the report demonstrates the progress that the project has made in Y4.

WP3/WP4 Team has pre-filled this table with available information. Please verify, correct if needed, complete, and make sure that all deliverables are uploaded both on the private project group of the One Health EJP website and on Zenodo.

Note that all deliverables should be public. In case of a scientific manuscript, be it the manuscript itself or the data supporting it, that cannot be publicised yet, you should upload a document that describes the work done (sampling, analysis, more or less the detail of the results, conclusions of the work, etc.).

The author of this document chooses the detail, which needs to be sufficiently clear for an external reader to assess the work done. This will especially be of importance at the end of the project when the project and its deliverables will be assessed by external reviewers.

Also assign a category (1 to 8) to each of the deliverables, as this helps PMT to assess possible impacts the outcome may have.

Deliverables

WP3 Team pre-filled the table below with available information. **Please verify, correct if needed and complete.** All deliverables due in 2021 (M37-M48) should figure in the table. If a delay is due to the COVID-19 crisis, please add a comment.

Link to Zenodo user guide: <https://zenodo.org/record/5603317#.YZZtkNDMJM0>

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
13	D-JRP13-1.1	Generation of a sequence database comprising publically available and newly generated sequences for <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> and <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. and	M30	M33		Zenodo link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4019840 Confidential on relevant WORLDCOM OHEJP website section, and already shared with all consortium members during development.	3

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		resistance genes CTX-M-15, NDM-5, KPC-2, OXA-48 and MCR-1.				Public	
13	D-JRP13-1.2	Novel machine learning algorithms for the prediction and detection of AMR from genomic sequences.	M48		M56	Confidential until full validation of the code or publication (except for WORLDCOM or other One Health EJP members). This deliverable has been delayed for several reasons: the late employment date in relation to COVID-19 restrictions, and the other commitments of this work package arising from collaboration with WP2-T1 – automated detection of LAMP assay data. Moreover, commitments with another OHEJP project and other pressing deliverables have delayed this progress.	
13	D-JRP13-2.1	Multiplex real-time isothermal assays for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes which will be suitable for use in laboratory and optimised further in WP3 into a format suitable for on-site use	M43	M43		Confidential until publication	
13	D-JRP15-AMR2.1-WP3.1	Lateral flow test for use on-site use together with Smartphone App for collection of data and transmission of test results to reference laboratory	M48		M50	Confidential until full validation of the code or publication (except for WORLDCOM or other One Health EJP members).	

[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

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JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
13	D-JRP13-5.1	Kick-off meeting organised	M25	M25		Brief report on KOM uploaded to ZENODO : Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5464662	
13	D-JRP13-5.2	DMP reviewed	M30	M33		The OHEJP WP4 team reviewed and approved WORLDCOM's online DMP in the CDP tool in December 2020.	3
13	D-JRP13-5.3	Organisation of project review meeting	M45	M45		WorldCOM consortium review meeting held in September 2021	
13	D-JRP13-5.4	Final 12 month technical and financial reports prepared for Year 3	M36	M38		Both technical and financial reports have been uploaded to Zenodo and can be accessed at: Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499692#.YTtQPp1KgdU	Other – project management

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

Milestones

WP3/WP4 Team has pre-filled the table below with available information. **Please verify, correct if needed and complete.**

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-01	Generation of sequence information for pathogens and resistance genes of interest.	M30	Y		Deliverable 1: Prevalence of ESBL subtypes in bacterial pathogens and a sequence database of selected alleles, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4019839
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-02	Transfer of relevant sequence information for development and training of novel machine learning algorithms.	M48	N	M56	Due to delays in the associated deliverable D-JRP13-1.2 arising from other commitments, the UoS is not yet ready to inform / receive the sequence information for training a machine learning algorithm.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-07	Performance testing of lateral flow or LAMP detection completed	M48	Y		All developed LAMP assays have been validated.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-08	Smartphone App for curation of assay results developed	M48	Y		The smartphone app has been successfully validated on example colorimetric LAMP assay results and further experiments have been planned to prepare a manuscript.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-11	Project review meeting organised	M45			Held in September 2021
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-12	Technical and financial reports prepared	M48	N		Technical report completed by M49. Financial reports will be completed by end of M49

4. Publications and additional outputs

Please make sure that you follow the publication policy: <https://zenodo.org/record/5598727#.YZZjxNDMJM0>

List peer-reviewed publications and others. For every publication please specify:

- **Doi reference**
- **Zenodo link**
- **Gold or green open access?**
 - o *If gold: Please specify the costs of the publication*
 - o *If green: Length of the embargo, if any. Open access to the publication must be ensured within a maximum of six months.*

If no doi reference (e.g. article in journal, publication in conference proceedings or workshop, book or monograph, chapter in a book, thesis/Dissertation, other), please provide as much information as possible.

Please make sure that all publications related to One Health EJP are listed.

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance dynamics of Escherichia coli in wastewater and river environments. Delgado-Blas JF, Ovejero CM, David S, Montero N, Calero-Caceres W, Garcillan-Barcia MP, de la Cruz F, Muniesa M, Aanensen DM, Gonzalez-Zorn B. Commun Biol. 2021 Apr 12;4(1):457. doi: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x (https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR)	YES		YES (2680 euros)
Emergence and dissemination of resistance mechanisms to last-resort antibiotics in human, animal and environmental bacteria [Thesis]. Delgado Blas, José Francisco (2021). ID Code: 64821. Director: González Zorn, Bruno			

Additional output

Other relevant dissemination outcomes can be highlighted here, e.g. non-scientific publications, proceedings, poster, video, tools, guidelines, patents, etc. If the outcome is a deliverable it should not be mentioned here. Please indicate where the item can be found, for instance on Zenodo or any open access repository. Indicate the link and check its functionality.

Posters

For WP1-T3 - an abstract entitled 'Automated detection of AMR target genes using loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP)' was submitted by PDRA Brian Gardner at UoS to the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9th-11th June 2021 in Copenhagen. This was selected as an e-Poster presentation.

For WP2-T2 and WP2-T3, poster entitled "Rapid detection and discrimination of closely related Enterobacteriaceae CTX-M group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, using an internally controlled multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay" was presented by Owen Higgins at the 2021 Microbiology Society conference, the OHEJP 2021 ASM, and the ECCMID 2021 conference.

For WP2-T1 and WP2-T2, posters entitled "Development of LAMP assays for the detection of key AMR targets in animal faeces and water samples" and "Rapid LAMP detection of key AMR targets for use as bed-side and/or pen-side diagnostics" were presented by Marwa Hassan at the 2021 Microbiology Society conference and the OHEJP 2021 ASM, respectively.

For WP2-T3, a poster entitled "Dynamics of quinolone- and cephalosporin-resistant *Escherichia coli* carriage along the production chain in Thuringian pigsties" was presented by Nicola Pfeifer at the OHEJP 2021 ASM.

For WP2-T1 and WP2-T2 an abstract entitled "Whole-genome sequencing of phenotypically characterized isolates from various settings" was presented by Vera Manageiro at the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9th-11th June 2021 in Copenhagen (e-Poster).

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

In this paragraph you have the possibility to draw the attention to achievements that could be highlighted to illustrate the potential impact of your project.

For WP1-T2, the publication "Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance dynamics of *Escherichia coli* in wastewater and river environments" (DOI: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x) developed within the framework of the WorldCOM project was published in Communications Biology, showing a global understanding of the AMR by integrating multiple genomic and functional analyses and comparing resistant *E. coli* populations from two distinct ecological niches, wastewater and river environments. The fundamental microbiological knowledge generated with this work contributes to the understanding of the genetic organization of environmental bacteria and establishes the basis for future studies in antimicrobial resistance dynamics.

5. Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

Shortly describe what links and cooperation exist with other projects or networks, within or outside One Health EJP. Relevant interactions with regional or national ministries or other authorities, and with organizations like ECDC and EFSA should be mentioned here, as this may reflect the beneficial outcome of the project.

NUI Galway participates in the MedVetKlebs OHEJP project, and is a member of the Med-Vet-Net association. Prof Morris is part of a JPIAMR network aimed at identifying robust, measurable surveillance indicators and methodologies for the monitoring of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the environment.

FLI participates in the JPIAMR consortia HECTOR and OASIS. HECTOR aims to identify determinants of host restriction of *Escherichia coli* strains and their potential association with AMR transmission and prevalence. OASIS aims to develop an AMR surveillance strategy, based on the Lot Quality Assurance Sampling approach, in a One Health context, and applicable in high-, middle-, and low-income countries.

UCM participates in the AVANT EU project, in ARDIG and FARMED, both from OH EJP, as well as in the MSCA CARTNET. Input from these projects will be relevant for WORLDCOM, and active participation between OHEJP projects will be encouraged for the benefit of OHEJP. Further, thanks to the application for Short Term Missions in OH EJP, Dr. Burke from NUI Galway visited the lab at UCM in summer 2021.

INSA is also participating in FED-AMR and FULL-FORCE projects from OHEJP, which outcomes will be important for WORLDCOM and vice-versa.

We are fully convinced that at the end of the project the tool obtained will be very useful, so it will be presented to EFSA and ECDC.

6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

The Ethic Advisors already accepted your comments. Therefore, this part of the report has been closed.

7. List of critical risks

Please indicate possible risk within your JRP/JIP

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	
Delay in work plan execution	Yes ¹
Conflicts within the consortium	
Lack of commitment of partners	
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	
Poor intra-project relationship	
Potential entry/exit of partners	
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information

¹Related with COVID lock down.

8. List of dissemination and communication activities

Please fill in one table per event you attended/organised in 2021.

You could choose either to report these activities by filling in the form below or by filling in the online form: <https://onehealthejp.eu/internal-events-survey/>

In order to help you with filling in this form, we have provided the figures (when available) related to the attendees numbers.

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021; Nicola Pfeifer poster presentation: 'Dynamics of quinolone- and cephalosporin-resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> carriage along the production chain in Thuringian pigsties'		
Date:	9-11 June		
Place:	Copenhagen, Zoom (Online)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Y
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	The Microbiology Society Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Dr Marwa Hassan poster presentation 1: 'Development of LAMP assays for the detection of key AMR targets in animal faeces and water samples'		
Date:	26-30 April 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:		One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Dr Marwa Hassan poster presentation 2: 'Rapid 'LAMP detection of key AMR targets for use as bed-side and/or pen-side diagnostics'	
Date:		9-11 June 2021	
Place:		Online	
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Dr Brian Gardner poster presentation: 'Automated detection of AMR target genes using loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP)'		
Date:	9-11 June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	The Microbiology Society Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Dr Owen Higgins poster presentation: 'Rapid detection and discrimination of closely related Enterobacteriaceae CTX-M group 1 variants, <i>bla</i>_{CTX-M-1} and <i>bla</i>_{CTX-M-15}, using an internally controlled multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-
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[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

	mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay'		
Date:	26-30 April 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Y
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021. Dr Owen Higgins poster presentation: 'Differential detection of CTX-M group 1 variants from <i>Escherichia coli</i> isolates using a multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay'		
Date:	9-11 June 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Y
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	

[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases (ECCMID) 2021. Dr Owen Higgins poster presentation: 'Rapid detection and discrimination of closely related Enterobacteriaceae CTX-M group 1 variants, <i>bla</i> _{CTX-M-1} and <i>bla</i> _{CTX-M-15} , using an internally controlled multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay'		
Date:	9-12 July 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Y
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	

[Date]

[name of meeting] hosted by [name of host institution] in [location]

Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021; Vera Manageiro poster presentation: 'Whole-genome sequencing of phenotypically characterized isolates from various settings'		
Date:	9-11 June		
Place:	Copenhagen, Zoom (Online)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Y
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number

Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Ryan Institute Centre for One Health Annual Conference 2021; Alexandra Chueiri oral presentation: "Rapid detection and discrimination of closely related Enterobacteriaceae CTX-M group 1 variants blaCTX-M 1 and blaCTX-M 15, using an internally controlled multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay"		
Date:	3-4 November		
Place:	Galway, Zoom (Online)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	Y
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	Yes
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	300	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			